

Employing the Once-Only Principle in the domain of the electronic public procurement

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Abstract. This paper presents a case study for the application of the “Once Only Principle” (OOP) for cross-border public services where citizens and businesses provide data only once in contact with public administrations. In order to support the European Union (EU)’s vision of a Single Digital Market, a generic federated OOP architecture has been developed, within the context of the European Union funded “The Once-Only Principle Project” (TOOP). The federated architecture is showcased in a real-life use case scenario that demonstrates in practical ways how OOP can be implemented to aid the elimination of administrative burdens in the domain of electronic public procurement. More specifically, the scenario focuses on the case of the Greek “European Single Procurement Document” (ESPD) public service, acting as a system that requests and receives data from the TOOP infrastructure. Finally, the paper presents the results of testing connectivity scenarios between the Greek and other Member State systems.

Keywords: Once-Only Principle • interoperability • eProcurement • data reuse • interconnection • cross-border public digital services

1 Introduction

There is no doubt, that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) systems are nowadays the core of government processes, and enterprise business as well. In addition, one of the core strategies of the European Commission is that of a Digital Single Market [1], meaning an internal European Union (EU) market that people are able to move freely and conduct their business outside of their home country, in any Member State. Thus, there is a significant need for citizens, enterprises and organizations to carry out their business seamlessly and easily in any Member State of the EU.

There are many practical difficulties though, for businesses engaging in cross-border activities. Things like, for example, complying with different national regulations or with different administrative requirements of foreign public agencies, form serious impediments. On the other hand, public agencies also face many difficulties when it comes to collecting, but also verifying the validity of foreign official information on companies and their legal representatives due to multiple data sources and the cost of manual

back-office procedures. In this context, the interaction with public services and the governments within the EU needs to be also reformed and digitally “transformed” to keep up with the new digital economic pace and reality. There are several steps to be taken though, in order to ensure the improvement of the delivery of services. These steps are made not only by providing tools, utilizing eGovernment practices and rethinking internal processes [2], but also by making them a significant priority through political commitment at the EU level. This kind of political commitment is showcased by the signing of the Tallinn Declaration on eGovernment at the ministerial meeting during Estonian Presidency of the Council of the EU on 6 October 2017 [3]. As part of this digital reform, the European Commission is taking concrete actions for the development of Cross-Border Digital Public Services [4], such as the creation of European interoperable platforms that implement the “Once-Only Principle” [5] (OOP) and the provision of guidelines for the better use of ICT systems of public authorities. Something that aims at aiding the plans of the EU regarding the Digital Single Market, by reducing the administrative burden in the Member States.

According to the “Once Only Principle”, sharing information and data across the public administration systems is cheaper than collecting them more than once from citizens and businesses. Thus, the OOP is based on the simplification of administrative processes and the notion that information is collected only once and then can become available and shared across the different systems that request for this information, respecting constraints that are imposed by regulations. This kind of digital information availability, not only increases the efficiency of the public administrations but also reduces the time and cost of the administrative processes, improving the quality of public services, both at national levels and cross-border [6].

To address the OOP related challenges and ease the implementation of OOP in cross-border settings, the Once-Only Principle Project (TOOP) [7] was selected and funded under the scope of the “EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Funding Programme” [8]. TOOP aims to facilitate the cross-border application of OOP by demonstrating it in practice through multiple real wide-scale pilots [9] using a federated architecture that is designed on a pan-European collaboration, enabling the connection of different registries and architectures in different countries and domains for better exchange of information across the public administrations [10]. TOOP’s main goal is to demonstrate the feasibility of its proposed federated architecture in real-world pilots. This means that the aforementioned pilots are systems that are either already in production, conducting real transactions connected to TOOP or are starting technical development and will reach production level within the lifetime of TOOP [11].

In order to explore the viability of TOOP’s proposed federated architecture, there are three pilot areas selected that serve as proof of feasibility across Europe. These pilot areas are the following:

1. Cross-border eServices for Business Mobility
2. Updating Connected Company Data
3. Online Ship and Crew Certificates

Each pilot area consists of different pilot use cases and usage scenarios that are of interest to the participating Member States. Such a particular use case scenario, of interest, is the Greek ESPD (European Single Procurement Document) system [12] which

demonstrates the use of OOP in the eProcurement domain within the first pilot area and it is further examined in this paper.

2 Background and Motivation for the study

2.1 Digital Single Market Strategy and Once Only Principle

In October 2015, the “Single Market Strategy” was introduced by the European Commission (EC) [13]. According to the EC, this strategy is “*at the heart of the European project*” [13], foreseeing that people, services, and goods are freely moving within the EU. The vision of the Single Market Strategy is backed by Initiatives and Action Plans, ensuring that citizens/businesses can fairly access goods and services, irrespective of their nationality and place of residence. One of the strategy’s backing Action Plans is the “eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020” [14].

The eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020 focuses “on the wide-scale implementation of eGovernment”, making sure that the citizens and businesses in the EU can experience the tangible benefits of technological enablers being used in public services. According to that, there are three policy priorities identified:

- *Public administration modernization using digital enablers such as Connecting Europe Facility (CEF)’s [15] building blocks (i.e. eID, eSignature, eDelivery, and eInvoicing);*
- *High-quality public services that ease the digital interaction between administrations and citizens/businesses;*
- *The facilitation of mobility of citizens/businesses by cross-border interoperability [14].*

To enhance cross-border activities within the EU, the introduction of the “Once Only Principle” (OOP) was made by the European Commission. According to the eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020, the EC defines the Once Only Principle as follows:

“public administrations should ensure that citizens and businesses supply the same information only once to a public administration. Public administration offices take action if permitted to internally re-use this data, in due respect of data protection rules, so that no additional burden falls on citizens and businesses” [14].

In October 2017, the Tallinn Declaration on eGovernment was signed by the ministers of 32 Member States of the EU. The declaration focuses on the benefits and potential savings to be achieved, through political commitment to “*take steps to identify redundant administrative burden in public services and introduce once-only options for citizens and businesses in digital public services*” [3]. Meaning that both the Tallinn Declaration and the eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020 establish the “Once Only Principle” and data re-use, as political priority and commits to reduce administrative burdens in public services.

2.2 Once Only Initiatives and Implementations

As part of the eGovernment Action Plan 2016-2020, two projects were funded under the “EU Horizon 2020” research and innovation program in order to address the OOP challenges: “The Once-Only Principle Project” (TOOP) and the “Stakeholder Community Once-Only Principle for Citizens” (SCOOP4C) [16]. TOOP, which was launched in January 2017 and is being coordinated by the Tallinn University of Technology in Estonia, focuses on reducing the administrative burden for businesses by employing the OOP. TOOP’s proposed solution is based on already existing working systems and building blocks in the Member States implementing “*multiple sustainable pilots by using a federated IT architecture on cross-border, pan-European scale.*” [17]. The SCOOP4C project, launched in November 2016 and coordinated by the University of Koblenz-Landau in Germany, aims to “*investigate, discuss, and disseminate how co-creation and co-production in public service provisioning for citizens can be achieved by implementing the once-only principle.*” [16].

Another case of an initiative employing the OOP is the Business Registers Interconnection System (BRIS) [18] providing cooperation across European business registers. It provides to the citizens and the businesses an interface for accessing information about companies and their branches across all Europe.

There are also many examples of using OOP in national implementations. For example, in the Netherlands, the Dutch Tax office provides pre-filled tax reports. Citizens don’t have to manually fill in tax forms, but only check and change things in case of an error [19].

2.3 eProcurement and the European Single Procurement Document (ESPD)

eProcurement refers to the exchange of supplies, services, goods and work through the Internet or any other electronic channels [20] and is the focus of the 2014/24/EU Directive [22]. According to the EC [21], “*public procurement is undergoing a digital transformation. The EU supports the process of rethinking of public procurement processes with digital technologies in mind.*” eProcurement is considered at the heart of EU Directives (2014/24/EU [22] on public procurement, 2014/23/EU [23] on the award of concession contracts). The purposes of these directives are enhancing the free movement of goods and services during procurement processes by making them simpler and easier for the Small Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) to gain access to procurement processes and bid for public contracts. Taking into consideration the lessening of administrative burdens and the continuation of the public procurement reform across the EU, the EC established the standard form for the ESPD [24] issuing an implementing regulation at January 5, 2016.

An ESPD “*is a self-declaration of the business’s financial status, abilities, and suitability for a public procurement procedure [25]. The access and participation in cross-border tendering opportunities is simplified since the tenderers no longer need to provide full documentary evidence and different forms previously used in the EU procurement. In addition, the service is available in all EU languages and can be used as*

preliminary evidence of condition fulfillment required in public procurement procedures across the EU” [26]. With the introduction of the ESPD, companies can participate in procurement processes without having to submit various documents as evidences satisfying certain criteria in order to participate. Only the winner of a procurement process needs to provide the actual documents and evidences. Almost all EU countries provide national ESPD services, since the use of the ESPD is obligatory. Also, since all Contracting Authorities are legally obliged to accept the standard layout of the ESPD, the Economic Operators can easily and safely qualify for any public tender in Europe increasing the competitiveness.

3 Methodology

3.1 The Generic Federated OOP Architecture

The aim of TOOP’s generic federated OOP architecture is to support the interconnection and interoperability between national registries at the EU level. The architecture consists of loosely coupled service components which utilize already existing available building blocks, such as the CEF [15] eID and eDelivery infrastructures and standards. The main benefit of re-using such components is the fact that they have already been used by the Member States and proven successful, avoiding the imposition of any technological specific solutions on citizens, businesses and public administrations. Fig. 1 shows a component architecture overview. A legal entity that can be either a natural or legal person is the user of a Public eService provided by a Member State. The Member State Authority providing the public service that requests and receives data from a registry in another Member State, acts in the role of Data Consumer (DC), whereas the Member State Authority providing the data acts in the role of Data Provider (DP). The TOOP infrastructure fetches information from the Member State Authority who acts as a DP making it available to the foreign Public Authority who acts as a DC. The end-user only needs to provide minimum information in order to be identified, authenticated and authorized allowing the TOOP infrastructure to discover what information is available for the needs of the DC Service. The cross-border interoperability is guaranteed via retrieving information in machine-readable format, packaged in a specific TOOP message format that uses the TOOP semantic building block in order to preserve meaning. In addition, an eDelivery Gateway is used providing secure transport between the DC and the DP and trust establishment between the participants.

As shown in Fig. 1, green components are deployed centrally either at TOOP or CEF infrastructure. Components in purple consist the TOOP connector, which is provided by TOOP as a facilitation, but Member States are free to replicate its functionalities using their own development. Components in blue are the responsibility of the Member State systems. It is worth to mention that since TOOP’s architecture is a reference architecture, there is no fixed way of how to deploy TOOP services. TOOP is providing components and guidelines as a facilitation but does not impose their usage.

The central components include the following:

- TOOP Directory: provides global search functionality over all participants,

- CEF BDMSL (Business Document Metadata Service Location): facilitates the retrieval of participant identifiers.
- Semantic Mapping Service: maintains mappings between national data models and the TOOP Common Semantic Model.

The services that need to be deployed at a Member State (MS) level are the following:

- Service Metadata Publisher (SMP) Service: decentralized registry that links identifiers to endpoint URLs and certificates for document exchange.
- eIDAS Node: Optional component that oversees identification and authentication of the user.
- TOOP Connector: Optional component that encapsulates several functions that support the data exchange from one participant to another. Some of its main functions are the transformation of data input into a proper TOOP message, routing metadata discovery and endpoint discovery. It is provided by TOOP as facilitation, but its usage is not imposed to the Member States.
- AS4 (Applicability Statement 4 standard for the secure and payload-agnostic exchange of business-to-business documents) Gateway: eDelivery Gateway that provides secure transport between the participants.

The DC User Interface, DC Business Processing and DP Business Processing components can vary and be specific to each Member State's eService.

Fig. 1 Component Architecture

3.2 ESPD Service as TOOP Data Consumer

3.2.1 Use case description

A typical usage scenario of the ESPD service with the TOOP integration is the following: Firstly, a Contracting Authority (CA) has published a call for tender containing among others the ESPD template for a specific call. The legal representative of an Economic Operator (EO) that wishes to take part in the tender process, gets the ESPD request from the public call for tender and is being authenticated to the ESPD service, providing information for the identification of the company for which creates an ESPD response and the country of origin. The ESPD service requests via the TOOP Infrastructure the requested information (i.e. company details) by the designated DP of the country of origin. The TOOP DP receives the request, processes it and sends a response back to the ESPD service. Upon a successful TOOP response reception from a DP, the ESPD service validates the response, extracts the available data from the response and after getting the user's consent, automatically fills the part of the ESPD form that is relevant with the requested information. Afterwards, the ESPD system asks of any additional information and generates the requested ESPD. The legal representative previews the generated ESPD response, completes and submits it and finally, proceeds with the tender process.

The EOs can easily and safely qualify for any public tender of a CA in Europe since all CAs are legally obliged to accept the standard layout of the ESPD. This fact makes the use case a perfect instance of demonstrating the elimination of redundant provision of data, by the legal representatives of the business's during the fulfillment process of an ESPD, through the TOOP infrastructure.

3.2.2 Advantages integrating TOOP with an ESPD Service

The provision of company details, as well as the provision of evidences to selection and exclusion criteria defined by the CAs is cumbersome for EOs, making them hesitant on participating in cross-border procurement procedures. Provision of a pre-filled version of the ESPD, through the TOOP infrastructure, alleviates some of the challenges that the EOs face, since it reduces the time and hassle of providing valid company data. Traditionally, these would have to be provided either in a form of a document (i.e. a certificate) or filled in by a business representative manually. The required data can be pulled directly from verified sources, such as the Business Registries that the EOs are registered, by connecting the Business Registries as TOOP DPs and the National ESPD/eProcurement services as TOOP DCs, thus avoiding information being submitted by the EOs more than once.

Furthermore, the eIDAS Regulation [27] is put into practice providing a predictable regulatory environment to enable secure and seamless electronic interactions between businesses, citizens and public authorities. People and businesses can use their own national electronic identification schemes (eIDs) to access public services in other Member States since companies that have their information in Business Registries that act as TOOP DPs, can access those data by using their eIDAS credentials. The ESPD

service that acts as a TOOP DC asks its users for their eIDAS credentials and consent for requesting any data required, respecting and taking into consideration regulations about the protection of personal data like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [28].

Data exchange is implemented in a way that reduces human interaction during the provision and consumption of the exchanged information, aiming as much as possible to machine-processable information sharing. In addition, the services are open to all Member States, avoiding bilateral agreements that do not scale EU-wide and thus, eliminating discriminations.

The ESPD service that acts a TOOP DC can connect and fetch data from every TOOP DP that is available in the TOOP eDelivery Network. There is no need for specific point-to-point connections due to TOOP's federated architecture. The TOOP DC requests for data and then the TOOP Infrastructure is responsible for the discovery and retrieval of the data.

Finally, the messages sent and received across the TOOP infrastructure are packaged, signed and encrypted in a certain way before transmission, ensuring their integrity, establishing trust between the TOOP DC and the TOOP DP.

3.2.3 The Greek ESPD Service as TOOP Data Consumer

Greece is participating in the TOOP infrastructure as a DC with the Greek ESPD service called "*Prometheus*". Each of TOOP's pilots deploy the required subset of TOOP service components necessary for the specific application scenario. Likewise, only the TOOP components necessary for the ESPD service scenario are deployed.

The implementation architecture, as shown in Fig 2, follows the TOOP architecture as described previously. The existing ESPD application is used without modification to its core components. A component called "*TOOP Interface*" acts as a bridge between the ESPD application and the rest of the TOOP infrastructure. The ESPD application can request data in its own format while the "DC Interface" (instance of TOOP Interface) converts that to a "TOOP Data Request" which is the proper request that can be made through the TOOP network. The "TOOP Response" that comes back can also then be converted to data that the ESPD application can work with.

Fig. 2 TOOP architecture of the Greek Data Consumer

4 Results

TOOP has defined a multi-step process to conduct tests that check the readiness and maturity of the pilot MS implementations. The last step of these series of tests is called a “Connectathon” which consists of thorough connectivity tests between a MS DC and a MS DP following the pilot scenario. When enough MSs are ready, a “Connectathon” can take place. In each “Connectathon”, every MS uses their implementation and attempt to exchange data with other MSs through a set of specified test scenarios. These include example sets of data and some test cases for the DP and DC software. The results of these exchanges are logged and discussed in order to address any issues that may come up. This method of testing was selected because it simulates a real-life scenario of exchanging data within the TOOP premises and aids in discovering issues with the TOOP components and the MS’ implementations.

Table 1. Successful Connections made with the Greek ESPD service acting as TOOP DC

#	DC	DP	Date
1	Greece	Sweden	23.05
2	Greece	Slovakia	23.05
3	Greece	Italy	07.06
4	Greece	Romania	04.07
5	Greece	Austria	16.09
6	Greece	Poland	16.09
7	Greece	Norway	26.09
8	Greece	Slovenia	26.09

Currently, the Greek ESPD Service acting as a TOOP DC has been successfully integrated and exchanged information with the Swedish, Slovakian, Slovenian, Italian, Romanian, Austrian, Polish and Norwegian systems acting as TOOP DPs, as it is shown in Table 1. The Greek ESPD service managed to exchange information with eight (8) different Member State systems by only connecting once to the TOOP infrastructure. There is no need for point-to-point connection between the Member States due to the way the TOOP federated architecture is designed.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

To sum up, this paper has focused on the ongoing work done in the General Business Mobility pilot area within the context of the TOOP project, especially the use case of the Greek ESPD Service, acting as a TOOP DC in the eProcurement domain. It is anticipated that more Member States will join, acting as TOOP DPs and demonstrate more cross-border exchanges. Finally, regarding the Greek ESPD service, there is ongoing work with the purpose of using the TOOP infrastructure to discover and retrieve Evidences and Documents, needed for the fulfillment of a CA's criteria requirements at the time of awarding or when is needed and not only fetching e.g. company data, thus eliminating the need for the businesses to upload documents from their local IT-infrastructure.

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